

Disease Prediction using various ML Approaches

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Abstract— The proposed system uses machine learning techniques to predict diseases based on symptoms given by patients or other users. It takes the user's symptoms as input and outputs a prediction of the patient's condition based on predictive modelling. Here, the notion of Supervised Machine Learning, which will be implemented using Light Gradient Boosting Machine, Random Forest, and Naive Bayes algorithms is used to aid in accurate disease prediction. The findings confirmed that the system is user-friendly and practical for individuals seeking quick disease diagnoses.

Keywords—Disease Prediction, Light Gradient Boosting Machine, Random Forest, Naive Bayes

I. INTRODUCTION

When someone is sick, they must go to the doctor, which is both time demanding and expensive. It would be simple if the aforementioned method could be performed automatically, saving both time and money. The prediction of diseases using patient symptoms is depicted in this research. The system uses python to apply machine-learning algorithms such as Light Gradient Boosting Machine, Random Forest, and Nave Bayes to forecast disease. It is accomplished through the application of leading-edge machine learning algorithms to ensure that the categorization correctly identifies those with disorders. Disease prediction is also challenging due to the fact that different diseases might have the same symptoms.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Kumar at el. [1] presented an illness prediction system that uses machine learning techniques to predict multiple disorders. In this scenario, use the concept of supervised Machine Learning, with Decision Tree, Random Forest, Nave Bayes, and KNN algorithms being used to aid in accurate disease prediction and better patient care.

Takke at el. [2] recommended a method of identifying and predicting the presence of a disease in a person using machine learning approaches such as Nave Bayes, Random Forest Classifier, K-Nearest Neighbors, and Support Vector Machines..

Chaturvedi at el. [3] developed a system that grab the user's symptoms as input and assesses the disease's likelihood. The Nave Bayes Classifier, Random Forest, and

Decision Tree are used to forecast disease. The disease risk is assessed using the Naive Bayes Classifier.

Dahiwade at el. [4] designed a model for prediction of the disease using approaches of machine learning and used techniques like KNN and CNN. This paper proposes disease prediction based on the patient's symptoms. KNN has a 95 percent accuracy rate, while CNN has a 98 percent accuracy rate.

Ubarhande at el. [5] To make predictions, use three machine learning algorithms: Nave Bayes, Random Forests, and Decision Trees. Following disease prediction, the system will provide detailed information about diseases as well as the ability to schedule an appointment with a certain doctor.

Chauhan at el. [6] proposed a disease prediction system that uses a decision tree algorithm to deliver greater disease prediction accuracy based on the user's symptoms, as well as inspiring ideas and images.

III. METHODOLOGY

The proposed method is based on predicting several diseases based on the patient's symptoms. The first step is to figure out what the problem is. Then it's time to get the dataset ready to work with. After then, think about the data. Finally, Machine Learning will be the major feature, which will employ the three methods;

- a. Light Gradient Boosting Machine,
- b. Random Forest
- c. Naive Bayes

which will accurately foresee disease for better patient care and early diagnosis. In addition, Machine Learning algorithms on the Python platform will be executed. In addition, an appealing graphical user interface (GUI) was created to allow users to interact with the system.

Fig 1: Working Model

A. Light Gradient Boosting Machine

LightGBM is a gradient boosting framework based on decision trees that enhances model efficiency while using less memory. It uses two novel techniques: gradient-based One Side Sampling and Exclusive Feature Bundling (EFB), both of which overcome the shortcomings of the histogram-based approach usually used in GBDT frameworks.. The other algorithms' trees grow horizontally, however the LightGBM algorithm climbs vertically, leaf by leaf, whilst the other algorithms grow level by level. LightGBM chooses the leaf that has suffered the most damage in order to grow. It can cut loss more than a level-by-level strategy while growing the same leaf.

B. Random Forest

This is a more complex type of decision tree in which N random records are chosen from a collection of symptoms. It is a supervised method in which the bagging method is used to create a huge number of classification and regression decision trees. It consists of a set of decision trees derived from a subset of the training set chosen at random, followed by a tally of votes from the various decision trees to arrive at a final prediction.

This mainly follows 4 steps:

- Take random samples from the dataset.
- Using each sample, create a decision tree and get a predicted result from each tree.
- Obtain a vote for each outcome in order to predict the outcome.

- The outcome will be selected by the last word guess with the most votes in total.

C. Naïve Bayes

It is a Bayesian probability theorem-based machine learning technique for categorization tasks. The most common application is text categorization, which necessitates large training the given datasets.

The Bayes theorem is used, which is defined as follows::

$$P(a | b) = P(b | a) \cdot P(a) / P(b)$$

- Where $P(a | b)$ is the probability of hypothesis.
- If hypothesis (a) is true, $P(b | a)$ is the probability that data (b) is true..
- $P(a)$ is the probability that hypothesis h is correct. (regardless of the data).
- $P(b)$ is the probability of the data (regardless of the hypothesis).

IV. BUILD MODEL

There is a various step taken part to prediction of diseases. The steps involved are:

1. Import the packages that are necessary.

```

from tkinter import *
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestClassifier
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.preprocessing import LabelEncoder
    
```

2. Upload and read training and testing dataset(Add the data into a DataFrame).

```

df=pd.read_csv("Training.csv")
tr=pd.read_csv("Testing.csv")
    
```

3. Training and testing.

```

x = df[11]
y = df[["prognosis"]]
np.ravel(y)

x_test= tr[11]
y_test = tr[["prognosis"]]
np.ravel(y_test)
    
```

4. Apply light gradient boosting machine approach and predict.

```

def LightGBM():
    from sklearn import tree
    import lightgbm as lgb

    clf3 = lgb.LGBMClassifier()
    clf3 = clf3.fit(X,np.ravel(y))

    predict = clf4.predict(inputtest)
    predicted=predict[0]
    
```

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the findings of the recommended system, which can be used to predict disease. A variety of Machine Learning approaches are used to produce the findings. To predict the disease, the Light Gradient Boosting Machine, Random Forest, and Naive Bayes algorithms are used. To predict the the ailment, the user can select up to five symptoms and then press one of three prediction buttons. This system also has a lovely user interface that captures all of the necessary data for the evaluation and makes it extremely user-friendly. This GUI shows the final output of our suggested system.

A. Implimentation

Fig 2: Sample Prediction 1

Fig 3: Sample Prediction 2

VI. CONCLUSION

The purpose of this study is to see if symptoms may be used to predict disease based on the data given. This machine is programmed to accept the user's symptoms as input and output an illness diagnosis. To make predictions, the suggested system used three Machine Learning techniques in this research. In addition, a user-friendly graphical user interface (GUI) was designed to make it easier for users to interact with the system. This study demonstrates how a range of characteristics and models can be utilized to predict disease using Machine Learning algorithms.

Finally, it can be concluded that the suggested system has no user threshold because anyone can use it. The purpose of this project is to develop an online platform that can predict illness development based on a variety of symptoms. The user will be able to choose from a number of symptoms and apply probabilistic predictions to identify diseases.

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